

MURAKKAB ARGUMENTLI TRIGONOMETRIK TENGLAMALARNI YECHISH

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Kosinuslar yig'indisini,
trigonometrik
tenqlamalar,
fakul'tataiv mashg'ulotlar

Trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechishning bir qancha standart va nostandart usullari mavjud bo'lib ularni yechishning turli usullari mavjud. Murakkab argumentli trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechish ko'p hollarda o'quvchilarga murakkabroq ko'rinadi. Ular tenglamani yecha olsalar ham javobni olishda nimalarga e'tibor berishlari kerakligini yaxshi bilmaydalar. Bunday tenglama va tengsizliklarni yechishni matematika to'garaklarida, fakul'tataiv mashg'ulotlarda o'rganilsa maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

1-misol. $\sin(\sin(\cos x - \sin x)) = 0$

tenglamani yeching. [1]

Yechish: $\sin(\cos x - \sin x) = \pi n, n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

$-1 \leq \sin t \leq 1$ bo'lgani uchun $-1 \leq \pi n \leq 1$

bo'lishi kerak. Bundan $n = 0$. Endi

$\sin(\cos x - \sin x) = 0$ tenglamani yechamiz.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada murakkab argumentli trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechish haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Bunday tenglamalarni yechishda nimalarga e'tibor berish kerakligi turli hil ko'rinishdagi tenglamalarni yechish orqali ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Bu $\cos x - \sin x = \pi k, k \in \mathbb{Z}$ tenglamaga teng kuchli.

$\sin(x - \frac{\pi}{4}) = \frac{\sqrt{2}\pi k}{2}$. k ning qiymati

$-1 \leq \frac{\pi k}{\sqrt{2}} \leq 1$ tengsizlikni qanoatlantirishi

kerak, bundan $k = 0$. Demak, $\sin(x - \frac{\pi}{4}) = 0$

tenglamani yechamiz. $x = \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi m, m \in \mathbb{Z}$

Javob: $\frac{\pi}{4} + \pi m, m \in \mathbb{Z}$.

2-misol. $\cos(\pi\sqrt{1 - \sin x}) = 1$

tenglamani yeching. [1]

Yechish: $\sqrt{1 - \sin x} = 2k, k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ bo'lishi

kerak. U holda $\sin x = 1 - 4k^2, -1 \leq \sin x \leq$

bo'lgani uchun $-1 \leq 1 - 4k^2 \leq 1,$

$-2 \leq -4k^2 \leq 0; 0 \leq k^2 \leq \frac{1}{2}$.

Demak, $k = 0$ va $\sin x = 1$.

Javob: $\frac{\pi}{2} + \pi n, n \in Z$.

3-misol.

$\sin^2(1 - \cos x) = \cos^2(1 + \cos x)$ tenglamani yeching. [2]

Yechish. Daragani pasaytirish formulasini qo'llab

$$\cos(2 + 2\cos x) + \cos(2 - 2\cos x) = 0$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Kosinuslar yig'indisini ko'paytmaga o'tkazib

$$\cos(2\cos x) = 0; \quad \cos x = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi n}{2}, n \in Z \text{ ni}$$

hosil qilamiz. n ning qabul qilishi mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlarini topish uchun

$$-1 \leq \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi n}{2} \leq 1 \text{ tengsizlikni yechamiz.}$$

Bundan $n = 0$ yoki $n = -1$. Demak,

$$|\cos x| = \frac{\pi}{4}$$

Javob: $\pm \arccos \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi k, k \in Z$.

4-misol. $\cos x + \cos \sqrt{x} = 2$

tenglamani yeching. [1]

Yechish: $|\cos x| \leq 1$ va $|\cos \sqrt{x}| \leq 1$ bo'lgani uchun berilgan tenglama quyidagi sistemaga teng kuchli

$$\begin{cases} \cos x = 1 \\ \cos \sqrt{x} = 1 \end{cases} \begin{cases} x = 2\pi k, k \in Z \\ x = 4\pi^2 m^2, m \in Z \end{cases}$$

Bundan $2\pi k = 4\pi^2 m^2; k = 2\pi m^2$, k va m lar butun son bo'lganligi uchun oxirgi tenglik $k = m = 0$ da o'rinli.

Javob: 0

5-misol. $\cos \sqrt{x} = \cos \sqrt{x+1}$

tenglamani yeching. [2]

Yechish: Berilgan tenglama quyidagi tenglamaga teng kuchli.

$$-2\sin \frac{\sqrt{x} - \sqrt{x+1}}{2} \sin \frac{\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{x+1}}{2} = 0$$

Bundan $\sin \frac{\sqrt{x+1} - \sqrt{x}}{2} = 0;$

$$\sin \frac{\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{x+1}}{2} = 0. \quad x \text{ ni topish uchun}$$

quyidagi 2 ta tenglamani yechamiz.

$$\sqrt{x+1} - \sqrt{x} = 2\pi k, k \in N;$$

$$\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{x+1} = 2\pi n, n \in N;$$

$x > 0$ da $\sqrt{x+1} - \sqrt{x} > 0$ bo'lganligi uchun $k \in N$

$x > 0$ da $\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{x+1} > 0$ bo'lganligi uchun $k \in N$.

Birinchi tenglamani yechamiz.

$$x+1 = x + 4\pi k \sqrt{x} + 4\pi^2 k^2;$$

$$4\pi k \sqrt{x} = 1 - 4\pi^2 k^2$$

Bu tenglama $k \in N$ da yechimga ega emas. Ikkinchi tenglamani yechamiz.

$\sqrt{x} = 2\pi n - \sqrt{x+1}$. Bu tenglama quyidagi sistemaga teng kuchli.

$$\begin{cases} x = 4\pi^2 n^2 - 4\pi n \sqrt{x+1} + x + 1; \\ 2\pi n \geq \sqrt{x+1} \end{cases}$$

Sistemaning birinchi tenglamasidan

$$\sqrt{x+1} = \frac{4\pi^2 n^2 + 1}{4\pi n}$$

$\sqrt{x+1} < 2\pi n, (n \in N)$ ekanligini

ko'rsatamiz. Haqiqatan ham,

$$\frac{4\pi^2 n^2 + 1}{4\pi n} < 2\pi n; \quad \frac{-4\pi^2 n^2 + 1}{4\pi n} < 0$$

Oxirgi tengsizlik $n \in N$ da o'rinli. Demak,

$$x = \left(\frac{4\pi^2 n^2 + 1}{4\pi n}\right)^2 - 1 = \left(\frac{4\pi^2 n^2 - 1}{4\pi n}\right)^2, n \in N$$

Javob: $\left(\frac{4\pi^2 n^2 - 1}{4\pi n}\right)^2, n \in N$

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